

Smoking does not accelerate leukocyte telomere attrition: a meta-analysis of 18 longitudinal cohorts

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ABSTRACT

Smoking is associated with shorter leukocyte telomere length (LTL), a biomarker of increased morbidity and reduced longevity. This association is widely interpreted as evidence that smoking accelerates LTL attrition. However, an alternative hypothesis is that individuals with shorter telomeres are more likely to start smoking. Both hypotheses predict a cross-sectional difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers, but the acceleration hypothesis additionally predicts an association between smoking and LTL attrition. We analysed the association between smoking and LTL dynamics in 18 longitudinal cohorts. The dataset included data from 12,579 adults (4678 current smokers and 7901 non-smokers) over a mean follow-up interval of 8.6 years. Meta-analysis confirmed a cross-sectional difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers, with mean LTL 78.83 bp shorter in smokers (95% CI: 21.09 to 136.58). However, LTL attrition was a negligible 0.44 bp/year faster in smokers than in non-smokers (95% CI: -1.83 to 0.95), a difference that equates to only 1.23% of the estimated age-related loss of 35.71 bp/year. Assuming a linear effect of smoking, at least 177 years of smoking would be required to generate the observed cross-sectional difference in LTL. It is therefore unlikely that smoking causes the difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers.

Key words: biological age, telomere length, telomere attrition, smoking, longitudinal.

IMPLICATIONS

Correlations between health behaviours and health-related biomarkers can arise for many reasons. We found no evidence to support the established belief that smoking affects one of the most commonly studied biomarkers of ageing—leukocyte telomere length. Our findings suggest that telomere length should be reinterpreted as a relatively static biomarker of some prior exposure as opposed to as a dynamic consequence of current smoking. Telomere length may be less useful than previously claimed for identifying behaviour that is harmful and for monitoring the consequences of behaviour change. More generally, our findings underline the need for caution when interpreting correlational data.

INTRODUCTION

Leukocyte telomere length (LTL)—the length of the repeated TTAGGG sequence at the end of leukocyte chromosomes—is an extensively studied biomarker of human health and well-being. In support of a link between poorer health and shorter average LTL, many cross-sectional studies have found an association between tobacco smoking and shorter LTL (1). Since human telomeres shorten with age, these data are widely interpreted as demonstrating that smoking accelerates the rate of biological ageing (1–3). For example, Valdes et al. (2) concluded, “Our findings suggest that obesity and cigarette smoking accelerate human ageing...smoking a pack a day for 40 years corresponds to 7.4 years of ageing”. Thus, the telomere data are invoked to support a more general claim that smoking is a potent gerontogen, or ageing accelerator (4,5).

The hypothesis that smoking causes telomere attrition is mechanistically plausible. Smoking causes increased levels of oxidative stress and inflammation (6–8), both of which are implicated in telomere attrition (9). *In vitro* studies show that oxidative stress increases telomere attrition by increasing telomere loss per cell replication in a dose-dependent manner (10,11). Smoking is therefore assumed to accelerate the rate of telomere attrition. Thus, although correlation does not provide evidence for causation, the hypothesis that smoking causes accelerated telomere attrition *in vivo* has been uncritically accepted based on cross-sectional data, and alternative explanations for the observed association between smoking and LTL have not been considered. However, evidence has started to accumulate that challenges this view. First, predicted links between oxidative stress and telomere attrition *in vivo* are proving elusive (12). Second, a Mendelian randomization study that used a genetic polymorphism (*CHRNA3* genotype) established to be strongly associated with tobacco consumption found no evidence to support a causal association between smoking and short telomeres (13). Finally, most of the variation in adult LTL is already present in early life, prior to the age at which most children start smoking, and adult LTL rank is largely stable (14,15). Thus, there appears to be little scope for smoking to influence variation in adult LTL. Our aim in the current paper is therefore to use longitudinal LTL data to test an alternative hypothesis of selective adoption, whereby individuals with shorter LTL are more likely to start smoking (16).

To generate testable predictions from the causation and selective adoption hypotheses we start by stating their assumptions (Fig. 1). For smokers, we assume that from the point at which an individual starts smoking their LTL in subsequent years can be modelled as a straight line with a positive intercept (c_s) corresponding to their LTL at the start of smoking, and a negative slope (m_s) corresponding to their LTL attrition per year of smoking. For age-matched non-smokers, we also assume that LTL can be modelled as a straight line with a positive intercept and negative slope with values c_n and m_n respectively. The causation hypothesis assumes that prior to starting smoking there is no difference in the LTL of future smokers and non-smokers (i.e. $c_s = c_n$), but that after starting smoking the rate of telomere attrition is higher for smokers than for non-smokers ($m_s > m_n$). By contrast, selective adoption assumes that prior to starting smoking future smokers have shorter LTL than future non-smokers ($c_s < c_n$), but after starting smoking the rate of LTL attrition is equal in smokers and non-smokers ($m_s = m_n$). Since causation and selective adoption are not mutually exclusive, we also consider a mixed hypothesis that assumes that future smokers have shorter LTL than future non-smokers ($c_s < c_n$) and after starting smoking the rate of LTL attrition is faster in smokers than in non-smokers ($m_s > m_n$).

Two major predictions emerge from Fig. 1 that are tested here. First, all three hypotheses predict that LTL for smokers should be shorter than LTL for non-smokers at any time-point following the adoption of smoking. Thus, the observation of shorter LTL in adult smokers

cannot be used to distinguish between the hypotheses. Second, the selective adoption hypothesis is unique in predicting that adult LTL attrition rate should be equal in current smokers and non-smokers, whereas the causation and mixed hypotheses both predict faster attrition in smokers. There have been a number of attempts to test this latter prediction using longitudinal LTL data within participants, but they have produced mixed findings (16). Whereas some studies report faster LTL attrition in smokers (17,18), others report no difference (19–24) and one study reports faster LTL attrition in non-smokers (25). To discriminate selective adoption from the other hypotheses it is critical to establish whether LTL attrition rates differ between smokers and non-smokers, and whether the observed difference in attrition is sufficient to explain the observed cross-sectional difference in LTL. Here we present the first quantitative meta-analysis aimed at estimating the effect of smoking on the rate of LTL attrition. This analysis was based on all datasets that we were able to identify that contained relevant longitudinal measurements of LTL and information on smoking status, regardless of whether the association between smoking and LTL dynamics had been previously published or not.

METHODS

Search strategy and data requirements

We sought longitudinal cohort studies in which baseline and follow-up measurements of LTL were obtained from each individual and in which data on smoking behaviour were also available. To allow sufficient time for biologically meaningful changes in LTL to be observed, we rejected cohorts in which the follow-up interval was less than 4 years (26).

We performed a systematic literature search using ISI Web of Knowledge (Thomson Scientific Technical Support, New York) for articles published prior to 2017 using the search terms: “telomere*” and “longitudinal” and “smoking”. Additional relevant articles were identified by snowballing (27). Articles were screened to identify potentially eligible cohorts. In many cases, determining the effect of smoking on LTL attrition was not the primary aim of an article, but smoking status was mentioned amongst the list of control variables.

In articles that reported estimates of the association between smoking and LTL attrition, the latter estimates usually came from multiple regression models that had been adjusted for baseline LTL. This practice is universal due to the strong association present in most datasets between baseline LTL and rate of LTL attrition arising largely as a consequence of regression to the mean (28). However, we have recently demonstrated that such adjusted estimates are likely to be biased in a direction that exaggerates the true effect of smoking on LTL attrition (29). Hence, we sought unadjusted estimates of the difference in LTL dynamics between smokers and non-smokers.

In two cases we were able to extract the required summary statistics from published articles, but for the majority of eligible cohorts, summary statistics on raw LTL and LTL attrition for smokers and non-smokers were not reported. Therefore, we contacted the authors and/or cohort managers to request either the required summary statistics, or the raw data. In nine cases authors or cohort managers calculated and supplied the required summary statistics, and in the remaining seven cases the first author obtained raw data and calculated the summary statistics herself. For nine cohorts there were some published findings available relating to the effect of smoking on LTL attrition rate (for a narrative review see(16)), but for the other nine cohorts the first author was blind as to the effect of smoking at the time of requesting the data.

The following data were obtained for each cohort included in the meta-analysis: the number of participants (smokers and non-smokers), mean age at baseline measurement (in years), mean follow-up interval (in years), LTL measurement method (TRF or qPCR), LTL measurement units (base pairs or T/S ratios), mean LTL at baseline and follow-up for smokers and non-smokers, standard deviation of LTL length at baseline and follow-up for smokers and non-smokers, annual rate of LTL attrition for smokers and non-smokers, standard deviation of LTL attrition per year for smokers and non-smokers and the Pearson correlation between LTL at baseline and follow-up measurements.

Participants were only included if they had LTL data at both baseline and follow-up; participants lost to follow-up were excluded. In cohorts in which LTL was measured at more than two time-points (LBC1921 and LBC1936) we only used the two LTL measurements that gave the longest follow-up interval for each subject, designating the first as baseline and the second as follow-up. LTL attrition rate for a subject was calculated via the following formula: LTL attrition rate (bp/year) = $(LTL_{\text{baseline}} - LTL_{\text{follow-up}}) / \text{follow-up years}$.

We sought to only include data from participants who were either consistent never-smokers or consistent current smokers at baseline and follow-up; where possible, we excluded participants who had quit smoking prior to baseline or between baseline and follow-up. For the majority of cohorts (15/18), smokers were defined as consistent current smokers at both baseline and follow-up and non-smokers were defined as consistent never-smokers at baseline and follow-up; individuals who changed smoking status between baseline and follow up were excluded. However, for one cohort (BRUNECK), smokers and non-smokers were defined based on baseline status only, and for the two cohorts, for which data were extracted from published papers (BHS and ESTHER), it was not clear whether the smoker/non-smoker classification was based on status at baseline, follow-up or both.

Statistical analysis

We analysed the data in the statistical programming language R, version 3.3.3 (30), using the meta-analysis package 'metafor' (31). The R script and dataset are available at: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.1240964](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1240964).

Since some cohorts reported LTL measurements in T/S ratios and others in base pairs, we computed standardised mean differences (SMDs) between smokers and non-smokers for LTL and LTL attrition. We used random-effects meta-analysis models and, unless otherwise stated, estimated parameters using inverse-variance weighting of cohorts (the default) and REML. To address the fact that we had two LTL measurements from each subject, and in some analyses we needed to either compare SMDs between time-points (Table 1, model 4), or combine SMDs across time-points (Table 1, model 5), we used the methods outlined in Borenstein et al. (32; chapter 24) for computing effect sizes from complex data structures involving multiple time-points.

To facilitate interpretation of the summary SMDs derived from the meta-analyses we transformed these effects into base pairs. To make these calculations, estimates of the standard deviations of either baseline LTL, or pooled LTL or LTL attrition rate were required, as appropriate. We estimated these standard deviations from the four cohorts measured with TRF (ADE, BHS, ERA and JLRCS), because these cohorts were the only ones for which LTL was originally measured in base pairs. The mean standard deviations for pooled LTL and LTL attrition rate derived from these four cohorts were 629.69 bp and 24.82 bp/year respectively.

RESULTS

Characteristics of the dataset

We obtained data from 18 longitudinal cohorts spanning 12 countries and four continents (Supplementary Information, Table S1). The combined dataset included data from 12,579 adults comprising 4678 current smokers and 7901 non-smokers. The mean age at baseline of the cohorts was 54.8 ± 15.4 years (mean \pm sd; range: 26.0-80.2). Given that tobacco use typically begins by age 16 (33), smokers in the dataset are likely to have already been smoking for at least a decade at the time of the baseline telomere measurement. The mean follow-up interval was 8.6 ± 2.2 years (mean \pm sd; range: 5.9-13.1).

Fourteen cohorts measured LTL using the quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) method and four used the terminal restriction fragment method (TRF; ADE, BHS, ERA and JLRCs; Supplementary Information, Table S2). The correlation between LTL at baseline and follow-up varied considerably among cohorts: Pearson correlation coefficients (r) ranged from 0 to 0.66 for qPCR measurements and from 0.92 to 0.97 for TRF measurements. These data suggest substantial variation in LTL measurement error among cohorts and greater measurement error in the subset of cohorts measured with qPCR.

Does LTL decrease with age?

To ascertain whether the telomere data were likely to be of sufficient quality to reveal effects of smoking on LTL dynamics, we first asked whether average LTL was shorter at follow-up than at baseline (when cohorts were a mean of 8.6 years younger). As expected, mean LTL was significantly shorter at follow-up, both in the meta-analysis and in all but one of the individual cohorts (Table 1, model 1; Supplementary Information, Fig. S1a). When we added the mean length of the follow-up interval to model 1 as a moderator, the slope of the meta-regression was in the expected direction, with longer follow-up intervals associated with larger declines in mean LTL between baseline and follow-up (Supplementary Information, Fig. S1b). Although the meta-regression was not significant overall (parameter estimate and 95% CI: -0.02, [-0.09, 0.04], $p = 0.4218$), it was significant for the subset of cohorts measured with TRF (parameter estimate and 95% CI: -0.03, [-0.05, <0.00], $p = 0.0186$). The estimated slope of the meta-regression was similar for both the whole dataset and the TRF subset, suggesting that although qPCR measurements are less precise, there is little evidence for bias.

Using the parameter estimate for the effect of age on LTL obtained from model 1 (Table 1) we calculated the estimated decrease in LTL between baseline and follow-up as 308.2 bp (95% CI: 225.0, 391.3). This equates to age-related attrition of 35.7 bp/year (95% CI: 26.1, 45.3), a value not significantly different from estimates of annual attrition obtained from longitudinal studies of LTL in cohorts not included in the current dataset (e.g. 40.2 bp/year (34) and 31.0 bp/year (35)). Thus, our data are of sufficient quality to show a robust effect of age on LTL of the expected magnitude over follow-up periods of as little as 5.9 years.

Do smokers have shorter LTL than non-smokers?

At baseline, smokers had shorter LTL than non-smokers in 17 cohorts and the difference was significant in four of these (Supplementary Information, Fig. S2a). At follow-up, smokers had shorter LTL in 15 cohorts and the difference was significant in four; non-smokers had significantly shorter LTL in one cohort (Supplementary Information, Fig. S2b). Meta-analyses showed that the association between smoking and LTL was significant overall at baseline and follow-up, with shorter LTL in smokers at both time points (Table 1, models 2 and 3

respectively). The causal and mixed hypotheses both predict that the difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers should increase over time (Fig. 1). Three cohorts followed this pattern with a significantly stronger association between smoking and LTL at follow-up and one cohort showed the opposite pattern with a significantly stronger association at baseline, but for most (14) of the cohorts, there was no difference in the association between smoking and LTL between baseline and follow-up (Fig. 2a). Meta-analysis of the difference in the association between smoking and LTL between time points showed that this was not significantly different from zero overall (Table 1, model 4). Thus, the pattern of cross-sectional findings within cohorts does not support the causal or mixed hypotheses (Fig. 1).

Since there was no evidence for a difference in association between time-points, we pooled the data to obtain a single, more powerful, estimate of the cross-sectional association between smoking and LTL for each cohort. Pooling across time-points yielded five cohorts with significantly shorter LTL in smokers, and meta-analysis confirmed significantly shorter LTL in smokers overall (Table 1, model 5). The parameter estimate of -0.13 that we report for this cross-sectional association between smoking and LTL agrees well with that of -0.11 reported by Astuti et al. (1) in their meta-analysis of 30 cross-sectional studies. In the current analysis, the observed association between smoking and LTL (from model 5) equates to smokers having telomeres 78.83 bp (95% CI: 21.09, 136.58) shorter than non-smokers.

There was significant heterogeneity among cohorts in the size of the association between smoking and LTL (Table 1, model 5). Given that most smokers start smoking in their teenage years, the causal and mixed hypotheses both predict that the difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers should increase as the mean age of the cohort increases. Our dataset allows a powerful test of this prediction, because mean age at baseline varies from 26 (in DMHDS) to over 80 years (in LBC1921; a far greater age range than the effect of follow-up interval analysed in model 4). To test this prediction, we added mean age at baseline as a moderator to model 5. The slope of the resulting meta-regression was not significantly different from zero (parameter estimate and 95% CI: <0.00 [-0.01, 0.01], $p = 0.9501$; Fig. 2b). Thus, there is no evidence that the difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers becomes larger in older participants who are likely to have smoked for longer. In conclusion, neither the within-cohort nor the among-cohort effects of age show the patterns in LTL predicted by the causal and mixed hypotheses (Fig. 1).

Do smokers have faster telomere attrition than non-smokers?

We used the longitudinal LTL attrition rates of participants to ask whether LTL attrition was faster in smokers than in non-smokers. Two cohorts (JLRCS and MONICA) had significantly faster LTL attrition in smokers, while one cohort (CCS) had significantly faster LTL attrition in non-smokers (Fig. 3a). Meta-analysis showed no significant association between smoking and the rate of LTL attrition overall, and no significant heterogeneity in the size of the association between cohorts (Table 1, model 6). The parameter estimate from model 6 equates to a difference in LTL attrition rate between smokers and non-smokers of -0.44 bp/year (95% CI: -1.83, 0.95). This difference in rate of attrition is a negligible proportion (1.23%) of the 35.7 bp loss per year that we estimated for ageing.

To establish the robustness of the lack of an association between smoking and LTL attrition, we conducted three further analyses of the rate of LTL attrition. First, to test whether any single cohort was having a substantial influence on the association between smoking and LTL attrition, we explored the effect of excluding each cohort from model 6 in turn. In all cases, the resulting parameter estimate for the association between smoking and LTL attrition was not significantly different from zero (Supplementary Information, Table S3). The inclusion of just

one cohort (MONICA) is responsible for the parameter estimate being negative; when this cohort is excluded, the parameter estimate for the association between smoking and telomere attrition was effectively zero (parameter estimate and 95% CI: < 0.00 [-0.05, 0.05], $p = 0.9947$).

Second, to test whether the lack of an association between smoking and LTL attrition is explained by the inclusion of cohorts with high LTL measurement error in the dataset, we re-ran model 6 weighting the contribution of each cohort by the correlation between baseline and follow-up LTL measurements (r ; a proxy for measurement error(26)). The resulting parameter estimate for the association between smoking and telomere attrition was now slightly positive and still not significantly different from zero (parameter estimate and 95% CI: 0.08 [-0.20, 0.36], $p = 0.5694$).

Third, we explored whether there was any evidence for bias in our selection of cohorts. We started with a systematic literature search, but due to the lack of suitable data in published articles, the final dataset that we assembled is an opportunity sample. For half of the cohorts included we had some idea of the effects of smoking expected due to information available in published articles (16), but for the remaining half we were blind to the expected findings at the time of requesting the data. Re-running model 6 on just the latter nine cohorts produced no change in the conclusion that smoking does not affect LTL attrition rate (parameter estimate and 95% CI: -0.04 [-0.17, 0.09], $p = 0.5797$).

Can the small difference in attrition explain the cross-sectional difference in LTL?

Although the difference in attrition between smokers and non-smokers was negligible and not significantly different from zero, attrition was still slightly faster in smokers (i.e. a negative parameter estimate) when we included all cohorts in the meta-analysis and weighted them in the conventional fashion (inverse-variance). Using the estimates of the difference in LTL from model 5 and the difference in attrition from model 6, we asked how many years of smoking would be necessary to generate the cross-sectional difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers. The parameter estimates from models 5 and 6 in Table 1 yield best estimates for the association between smoking and LTL of -78.83 bp, and between smoking and LTL attrition rate of -0.44 bp/year. Thus, assuming a linear effect of smoking on attrition, 177.45 years of smoking would be required to generate the observed cross-sectional difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers. When we weighted cohorts by their measurement error in model 6, LTL attrition was estimated as slightly higher in non-smokers than smokers (0.08 bp/year). Under this scenario, no number of years of smoking can generate the observed baseline difference in LTL.

Is the effect of smoking on the rate of LTL attrition non-linear?

Thus far, our tests of the causal hypothesis have assumed a linear effect of smoking on the rate of LTL attrition that continues unabated in smokers (Fig. 1). To test whether an effect of smoking on the rate of LTL attrition is present in newer smokers and diminishes or reverses over time, we added age at baseline as a moderator to model 6. The slope of the resulting meta-regression was not significantly different from zero (parameter estimate and 95% CI: < 0.00 [-0.00, 0.01], $p = 0.3019$; Fig. 3b). Thus, there is no evidence for an association between smoking and LTL attrition in younger people, who have more recently started smoking, that subsequently diminishes over time.

DISCUSSION

Using meta-analytic methods to compare LTL dynamics over a mean of 8.6 years of follow-up in 4678 current smokers and 7901 non-smokers, we found no evidence for significantly faster

telomere attrition in smokers. Our analyses confirmed that LTL shortened with increasing age and that smokers had shorter LTL than non-smokers at all measured time-points. However, there was no evidence that this cross-sectional difference increased with age, as would be expected if smoking causes LTL attrition. There was also no significant difference in the rate of LTL attrition measured within smokers and non-smokers. Moreover, the negligibly greater rate of attrition observed in smokers was totally insufficient to produce the cross-sectional difference between smokers and non-smokers within a human lifetime. Taken together, these findings provide no support for the hypothesis that smoking causes LTL attrition.

The above conclusion is based on assuming a linear effect of smoking on telomere attrition over time (Fig. 1). There are strong mechanistic reasons for assuming a linear model. Current smoking causes a chronic elevation in the levels of oxidative stress and inflammation, both of which are implicated in accelerated telomere attrition in a dose-dependent manner. However, some authors have attempted to explain the lack of an effect of smoking on telomere attrition in previous studies by assuming that smoking has an initial accelerating effect on attrition that rapidly reverses with continued smoking (19–21). The evidence claimed for this non-linear effect is the strong positive correlation observed in all longitudinal studies between baseline telomere length and telomere attrition: individuals starting with longer telomeres have faster attrition than those starting with shorter telomeres. On the basis of this observation, Farzaneh-Far et al. (21) have argued that any rapid initial shortening of telomeres caused by smoking is subsequently offset by a length-related decrease in attrition caused by this ‘homeostatic’ process. However, it has now been recognized that a more parsimonious explanation for the observed correlation between baseline LTL and attrition rate is regression to the mean resulting largely from measurement error (28). Thus, the apparent ‘homeostatic’ mechanism proposed to account for non-linear attrition rates in smokers is largely a statistical artefact. Importantly, our analysis of the current dataset provided no evidence that the association between smoking and LTL attrition changed over time as would be expected if an effect of smoking was present early on and subsequently diminished or reversed. It is a limitation of our dataset that our youngest cohorts were already in their 20’s, meaning that the majority of smokers are likely to have been smoking for at least a decade. It is therefore possible that we could have missed an effect of smoking on LTL attrition that occurred prior to the baseline telomere measurements.

Is the lack of an effect of smoking on telomere attrition a limitation of low power? Some authors have argued that longitudinal studies have low power for detecting effects of smoking on attrition due to their small sample sizes (19,20,25). While it is often the case that sample sizes are larger in cross-sectional than longitudinal studies, this is not true of the 18 cohorts included in the current analysis, where the same individuals were studied both cross-sectionally and longitudinally. Furthermore, longitudinal studies eliminate the substantial between-individual variation in LTL by measuring within-individual changes in LTL and are therefore much more powerful than cross-sectional studies of the same sample size for detecting effects of smoking on telomere dynamics (36). Importantly, our meta-analysis of 18 longitudinal datasets shows no significant heterogeneity among cohorts in the effect of smoking on telomere attrition rates. This suggests first, that it is valid to compute a summary estimate for the difference in attrition between smokers and non-smokers, and second, that the precision of the meta-analysis exceeds that of its constituent cohorts (32). The resulting negligible difference in attrition between smokers and non-smokers of -0.44 bp/year is therefore the most powerful estimate yet of the association between smoking and telomere attrition.

What is the likely impact of telomere measurement error on our findings? The variation in the correlation between baseline and follow-up LTL measurements suggests substantial variation

in measurement error among cohorts(26). While this error should not cause bias in our estimates of the association between smoking and LTL attrition, it will affect the precision of these estimates (29). We found no evidence that weighting cohorts according to the correlation between baseline and follow-up measurements caused a significant change in our estimate of the association between smoking and LTL attrition. Indeed, the weighted meta-analysis actually yielded a marginally lower rate of LTL attrition in smokers compared to non-smokers. This result strengthens the evidence against the causal hypothesis, because it implies that no amount of smoking could yield the observed cross-sectional difference in LTL.

Is it possible that some kind of bias is masking a true effect of smoking on telomere attrition? Restricting our dataset to participants that survived to follow-up undoubtedly introduces selection based on mortality (e.g. 25). Since both smoking and short LTL have been argued to cause earlier mortality, mortality is a collider variable in our analyses. Selection based on the value of a collider is usually discussed in the context of producing spurious associations between independent variables, so-called 'collider bias' (e.g. 37), but collider bias can also potentially mask true associations. For example, by selecting against individuals who die between baseline and follow-up, longitudinal studies could underestimate the effects of smoking on telomere attrition, because they retain only smokers who are resistant to the damaging effects of tobacco smoke. However, this argument fails to explain the substantial difference in baseline LTL between smokers and non-smokers that we observed, even in the studies where the age of participants at baseline was quite advanced. If selection bias is present, it should affect cross-sectional associations as well as measures of attrition. Furthermore, selection based on mortality should be negligible in cohorts in their 20s or 30s, but substantial for cohorts over 60, yet we found no effect of baseline age on the size of the association between smoking and LTL attrition, despite an age range of over 54 years. Taken together, the above findings argue against collider bias masking a true association between smoking and LTL attrition.

We deliberately elected to use raw attrition measures in our analyses as opposed to effect sizes derived from multiple regression models controlling for known sources of variation in telomere attrition rates (such as baseline telomere length). Our rationale for this choice came from recent work showing that controlling for baseline telomere length in multiple regression models of telomere attrition biases the effects of any predictor variables that also correlate with telomere length at baseline (typically age, sex and smoking status; (29)). This latter finding suggests that the published effects of variables such as age, sex and smoking status on telomere attrition are likely to exaggerate the true effect sizes of these variables, raising the probability of type I errors above 5% (see also 38). This could explain why some of our individual cohorts report significant effects of smoking on LTL attrition (17,18).

Our findings do not support the hypothesis that smoking is the sole cause of differences in LTL between smokers and non-smokers. Accordingly, we conclude that selective adoption of smoking by individuals with short telomeres is likely to be occurring. Selective adoption predicts that a difference in LTL between future smokers and non-smokers should exist prior to the start of smoking. A conclusive test of selective adoption therefore requires measurement of LTL in children prior to the start of smoking combined with longitudinal follow-up on adoption of smoking behaviour. We are not aware of any currently existing cohorts in which this prediction can be tested.

Two alternative causal pathways could underlie selective adoption (16). First, it is possible that telomere shortening could directly cause changes in behaviour. While there is no data relating specifically to genes linked to behaviour, there is emerging evidence that telomere shortening

causes changes in regulation of more than 140 genes (39,40), making this idea theoretically possible. A second causal pathway yielding selective adoption is that exposure to a third variable both shortens LTL and makes subsequent adoption of smoking more likely. One possibility, that still attributes a causal role to smoke exposure, is that parental smoking both causes early-life LTL attrition and increases a child's probability of starting smoking. A recent study found that telomere loss between birth and young adulthood was positively associated with distance to a major road at the residential address occupied at birth (41), suggesting air pollution as a possible cause of childhood telomere attrition. Thus, it is possible that passive smoking in early life could cause telomere attrition. However, it is not necessary to attribute any causal role to smoke exposure to explain the data in the current paper. We suggest that a plausible third variable supported by substantial existing data is exposure to early-life adversity. Developmental telomere attrition is accelerated by exposure to early-life adversity of various types including family disruption and physical and emotional abuse (42–45). Furthermore, these same sources of early-life adversity are also associated with a greater probability of starting smoking, smoking more and being less likely to quit (46–48). Thus, although childhood LTL has not thus far been examined as a predictor of adult smoking behaviour, there is strong indirect evidence to expect an association to exist.

In conclusion, we find no evidence that smoking accelerates the rate of leukocyte telomere attrition in adults. Our findings should prompt more critical appraisal of data underlying the claim that smoking is the most important, 'broad range' ageing accelerator (4,5). Where these data come from cross-sectional studies, and *in vivo* experimental studies are lacking, we suggest that selective adoption should be considered as an alternative explanation for associations between smoking and biomarkers of ageing such as telomere length.

Our findings have consequences for how measures of telomere length are used in human epidemiology and behavioural ecology. Under the currently prevailing view that certain types of behaviour cause accelerated telomere attrition, measures of telomere length can be used to identify those behaviours that are most harmful and those that are protective (49). Changes in telomere dynamics could also potentially be used to monitor the somatic consequences of behaviour change (e.g. the positive effects of quitting smoking). However, if we are correct, and selective causation turns out to be an explanation for observed associations with telomere length, then we need to reinterpret shorter telomeres as a relatively static biomarker of early-life experience as opposed to as a dynamic consequence of current adult behaviour.

DATA ACCESSIBILITY

An R script that generates the figures and analyses presented in this paper and the necessary dataset are publically available at: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.1240964](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1240964).

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RESEARCH ETHICS

No additional ethical permission was required for this study because the analysis was based on secondary analysis of existing data.

COMPETING INTERESTS

We have no competing interests.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceived the study, analysed the data and wrote the paper: MB and DN; assisted in identification of cohorts: CMM-R and GVP; provided summary statistics: FK and PW (BRUNECK), SEB and BGN (CCHS), WMT (DMHDS), CM and MW (HSS), AA and JK (JLRCS), LB (MONICA), DR and BWJH (NESDA), PvdH and MAS (PREVEND), SH and YZ (SATSA); provided raw data: AB and CL (ADE, ERA), YB-S (CCS), CC and HS (HAS), RC and DK (NSHD), IJD, SEH and JMS (LBC1921 and LBC1936); ran original LTL measurements CMM-R and TvZ (CCS, HAS, LBC1921, LBC1936, NSHD); edited and approved the final manuscript: all authors.

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Table 1. Results from random-effects meta-analytic models on data from 18 cohorts.

Model		Summary SMD		Heterogeneity statistics					Forest plot
		Estimate* [95% CI]	p-value	Q ₁₇	p-value	τ ²	I ² (%)	H ²	
1	Difference in LTL between time points	-0.49 [-0.62, -0.36]	<0.0001	333.73	<0.0001	0.07	95.89	24.31	Fig. S1a
2	Assn. between smoking and baseline LTL	-0.10 [-0.16, -0.05]	0.0003	26.55	0.0650	0.01	44.70	1.81	Fig. S2a
3	Assn. between smoking and follow-up LTL	-0.15 [-0.29, -0.01]	0.0312	95.13	<0.0001	0.06	89.78	9.78	Fig. S2b
4	Difference in assn. between smoking and LTL between time points	-0.05 [-0.16, 0.06]	0.3884	73.45	<0.0001	0.04	90.41	10.43	Fig. 2a
5	Pooled assn. between smoking and LTL	-0.13 [-0.22, -0.03]	0.0075	85.62	<0.0001	0.03	83.96	6.24	Not shown
6	Assn. between smoking and LTL attrition	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.5311	24.68	0.1021	0.00	36.48	1.57	Fig. 3a

*Negative parameter estimates for the summary standardized mean difference (SMD) correspond to: model 1 - shorter LTL at follow-up; models 2, 3 and 5 - shorter LTL in smokers; model 4 – stronger assn. between smoking and LTL at follow-up; model 6 - faster attrition in smokers. Significant associations are shown in bold.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Fig. 1. Three alternative models to explain the observed association between smoking and LTL: (a) causation, (b) selective adoption, and (c) mixed (= causation + selective adoption). We assume that smoking starts at t_0 for smokers and continues thereafter, whereas non-smokers never smoke. The magenta line represents the telomere dynamics for smokers and the green line for age-matched non-smokers. The dotted lines represent two measurements of adult LTL (baseline and follow-up) made after the start of smoking.

Fig. 2. The difference in LTL between smokers and non-smokers does not increase with more years of smoking. (a) Forest plot showing the lack of difference in association between smoking and LTL between baseline and follow-up (model 4). The squares show the observed standardized difference (SMD) and the whiskers the 95% CI for each cohort; the area of each square is proportional to the weight given to that cohort in the meta-analysis. Cohorts measured with qPCR are shown in red and cohorts measured with TRF in blue. Significant differences are shown in bold. The black diamond shows the meta-analytic summary: the center depicts the mean effect and the width the 95% CI. (b) Scatterplot showing that the association between smoking and LTL does not change as mean age at baseline increases. Each point represents one cohort and the area of the point is proportional to the weight in model 4. The solid black line shows the non-significant estimate from a random-effects meta-regression model obtained by adding mean age at baseline as a moderator to model 5. The ribbon shows 95% CI for the estimate. The dashed line indicates no effect of smoking on LTL.

Fig. 3. The rate of LTL attrition is virtually identical in smokers and non-smokers and this absence of a difference in attrition does not change over 54 years of smoking. (a) Forest plot showing the lack of an association between smoking and LTL attrition rate measured longitudinally within participants (model 6). (b) Scatterplot showing the lack of association between the effect of smoking on LTL attrition and mean age at baseline. The solid black line shows the non-significant estimate from a random-effects meta-regression model obtained by adding mean age at baseline as a moderator to model 6. The dashed line indicates no association between smoking and LTL attrition. For key see Fig. 2.

FIGURES

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Supplementary Information: Table S1. Details of the cohorts included.

Cohort (acronym)	Country	Mean age at baseline (years)	Mean follow-up interval (years)	Number of participants with consistent smoking status over the follow-up interval ¹		Source of TL data ²	Reference for cohort
				Smokers	Non-smokers		
ADELAHYDE (ADE)	France	68.3	8.3	2	42	Raw	(50)
Bogalusa Heart Study (BHS)	USA	31.4	5.9	214	421	Extracted	(19)
Bruneck Study (BRUNECK)	Italy	58.6	10.0	114	307	Summary	(20)
Copenhagen City Heart Study (CCHS)	Denmark	52.7	9.4	1402	1455	Summary	(24)
Caerphilly Cohort Study (CCS)	Wales, UK	64.4	8.0	106	154	Raw	(51)
Dunedin Multidisciplinary Health and Development Study (DMHDS)	New Zealand	26.0	12.0	173	458	Summary	(52)
Evolution de la Rigidité Artérielle (ERA)	France	59.8	9.5	1	86	Raw	(23)
Epidemiological Study on the Chances of Prevention, Early Recognition, and Optimised Treatment of Chronic Diseases in the Older Population (ESTHER)	Germany	61.3	8.0	116	1696	Extracted	(25)
Hertfordshire Ageing Study (HAS)	England, UK	67.1	9.3	20	87	Raw	(51)
Heart and Soul Study (HSS)	USA	66.1	4.8	76	475	Summary	(21)
Jerusalem LRC Study (JLRCS)	Israel	30.1	13.1	154	275	Summary	(53)
Lothian Birth Cohort 1921 (LBC1921)	Scotland, UK	80.2	9.1	3	76	Raw	(51)
Lothian Birth Cohort 1936 (LBC1936)	Scotland, UK	69.6	6.0	62	406	Raw	(54)
Danish MONICA1 and 10 survey (MONICA)	Denmark	44.1	10.9	532	603	Summary	(17)
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Netherlands	40.8	6.0	455	489	Summary	(22)
MRC National Survey of Health and Development (NSHD)	England, UK	53.4	9.3	112	326	Raw	(51)
Prevention of Renal and Vascular End-Stage Disease (PREVEND)	Netherlands	46.6	6.5	1091	1456	Summary	(18)
Swedish Adoption/Twin Study of Aging (SATSA)	Sweden	66.7	9.4	45	302	Summary	(55)

¹These numbers are often smaller than the numbers given in the original reference for the cohort due to the fact that we only included participants with consistent smoking status between baseline and follow-up (see Methods for details). ²Data sources: Raw = raw TL data obtained from cohort manager and summary statistics calculated by corresponding author (MB); Extracted = summary statistics extracted from published article (reference in final column); Summary = summary statistics calculated and supplied by co-authors (see author contributions for details).

Supplementary Information: Table S2. Summary of LTL data used in the meta-analysis.

Cohort ¹	LTL measurement		Baseline TL				Follow-up TL				Telomere attrition (/year)				Pearson correlation between baseline and follow-up LTL	
	Method ²	Units ³	Smokers		Non-smokers		Smokers		Non-smokers		Smokers		Non-smokers		r	p-value
			Mean	sd	Mean	sd	Mean	sd	Mean	sd	Mean	sd	Mean	sd		
ADE	TRF	bp	6290.00	721.25	6378.57	465.85	6155.00	855.60	6128.57	490.83	16.44	15.56	30.02	24.20	0.92	<0.0001*
BHS	TRF	bp	7392.00	777.00	7481.00	777.00	7150.00	772.00	7270.00	772.00	42.00	46.00	40.00	46.00	0.95	<0.0001*
BRUNECK	qPCR	T/S	1.64	0.83	1.68	0.84	1.15	0.61	1.18	0.55	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.64	<0.0001*
CCHS	qPCR	bp	4318.00	1047.00	4434.00	1062.00	4042.00	1010.00	4116.00	1031.00	28.00	120.00	33.00	122.00	0.39	<0.0001*
CCS	qPCR	bp	4302.39	1591.62	4506.89	1867.65	3438.83	1472.86	3080.53	938.18	112.76	288.71	183.06	261.03	0.03	0.5990
DMHDS	qPCR	T/S	1.17	0.37	1.20	0.41	1.02	0.31	1.05	0.31	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.66	<0.0001*
ERA	TRF	bp	5860.00	0.00	6428.84	620.03	5710.00	0.00	6198.26	601.17	16.04	0.00	24.34	15.52	0.97	<0.0001*
ESTHER	qPCR	bp	5940.00	384.49	6020.00	315.18	5190.00	522.04	5810.00	616.72	1.30	84.35	14.50	99.80	NA	NA
HAS	qPCR	bp	5490.26	1464.64	5417.45	1443.86	3637.15	1539.88	4048.20	1446.62	204.74	265.92	149.04	236.01	-0.16	0.0919
HSS	qPCR	bp	5546.32	543.21	5483.28	527.85	5325.56	406.29	5277.76	344.28	46.12	119.89	42.05	102.77	0.40	<0.0001*
JLRCS	TRF	bp	7253.00	650.00	7361.00	673.00	6907.00	590.00	7053.00	644.00	26.50	14.00	23.50	13.60	0.96	<0.0001*
LBC1921	qPCR	bp	3912.37	301.05	4096.44	457.96	3290.00	770.88	3542.61	791.46	49.64	33.08	64.34	138.97	0.35	0.0017*
LBC1936	qPCR	bp	4073.34	579.07	4207.34	571.33	3680.81	648.08	3805.03	708.36	86.94	119.95	66.38	112.14	0.54	<0.0001*
MONICA	qPCR	T/S	0.75	0.16	0.74	0.16	0.65	0.19	0.67	0.20	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.37	<0.0001*
NESDA	qPCR	bp	5407.29	623.56	5511.60	614.67	5370.51	403.03	5440.66	446.86	6.13	96.55	11.82	95.26	0.45	<0.0001*
NSHD	qPCR	bp	5610.81	2017.47	5792.41	1827.71	4241.11	1236.59	4297.16	1345.08	148.61	235.88	160.14	234.61	0.12	0.0102*
PREVEND	qPCR	T/S	1.05	0.32	1.09	0.32	1.00	0.36	1.07	0.35	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.07	0.13	<0.0001*
SATSA	qPCR	T/S	0.73	0.19	0.73	0.22	0.72	0.15	0.74	0.17	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.39	<0.0001*

¹Full details of each cohort are provided in Table S1; ²Measurement methods for LTL: TRF = terminal restriction fragment and qPCR = quantitative polymerase chain reaction; ³Units of LTL measurement: bp = base pairs and T/S = T/S ratios.

Supplementary Information: Table S3. Results from sensitivity analysis of model 6.

Cohort omitted	Summary SMD		Heterogeneity statistics				
	Estimate* [95% CI]	p-value	Q ₁₆	p-value	τ^2	I ² (%)	H ²
ADE	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.5116	24.06	0.0881	0.00	37.93	1.61
BHS	-0.02 [-0.08, 0.05]	0.6091	24.56	0.078	0.01	41.03	1.70
BRUNECK	-0.02 [-0.08, 0.04]	0.5257	24.64	0.0764	0.00	40.44	1.68
CCHS	-0.03 [-0.09, 0.03]	0.3793	21.65	0.155	0.00	32.98	1.49
CCS	-0.03 [-0.08, 0.03]	0.2978	19.97	0.2215	0.00	30.71	1.44
DMHDS	-0.02 [-0.08, 0.04]	0.5217	24.61	0.077	0.01	40.93	1.69
ERA	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.5214	24.39	0.0814	0.00	37.93	1.61
ESTHER	-0.03 [-0.08, 0.03]	0.3552	22.49	0.1282	0.00	34.74	1.53
HAS	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.5973	23.93	0.091	0.00	38.05	1.61
HSS	-0.02 [-0.08, 0.04]	0.5721	24.64	0.0764	0.00	40.12	1.67
JLRCS	-0.01 [-0.06, 0.05]	0.8152	20.47	0.1996	0.00	29.70	1.42
LBC1921	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.5256	24.64	0.0765	0.00	38.03	1.61
LBC1936	-0.01 [-0.07, 0.05]	0.6828	23.16	0.1096	0.00	36.99	1.59
MONICA	0.00 [-0.05, 0.05]	0.9947	18.39	0.3017	0.00	13.68	1.16
NESDA	-0.03 [-0.09, 0.03]	0.3918	23.27	0.1068	0.00	36.71	1.58
NSHD	-0.02 [-0.08, 0.04]	0.4743	24.33	0.0825	0.00	39.61	1.66
PREVEND	-0.01 [-0.08, 0.05]	0.6692	23.98	0.09	0.01	38.68	1.63
SATSA	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.04]	0.6088	24.25	0.0841	0.00	38.80	1.63

*Negative parameter estimates for the summary standardized mean difference (SMD) correspond to faster attrition in smokers. The cohort with the largest influence is shaded.

Supplementary Information: Fig. S1. LTL decreases with increasing age. (a) Forest plot showing that LTL is significantly shorter at follow-up compared to baseline. (b) Scatterplot showing that longer follow-up intervals are associated with a greater decline in LTL between baseline and follow-up. The black line shows the estimate from a random-effects meta-regression obtained by adding mean follow-up interval as a moderator to model 1; this estimate is based on all 18 cohorts in the plot. The blue line shows the estimate from the same meta-regression ($\pm 95\%$ CI) based on the subset of cohorts measured using TRF. For key see Fig. 2.

Supplementary Information: Fig. S2. Smokers have shorter LTL than non-smokers at both baseline and follow-up. Forest plots showing the significant associations between smoking and LTL at (a) baseline (model 2), and (b) follow-up (model 3). For key see Fig. 2a.